

METHODOLOGY OF FORMING PERSONAL QUALITIES OF PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS BASED ON SPORTS GAMES

Madaminov Mirjalol Polat ugli

Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of the "Physical Culture" department of the

Faculty of Exact and Applied Sciences

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Annotation: This thesis discusses the content and methods of developing physical and personal qualities of future primary education teachers through action games.

Key words: Physical education, human development, national values, formation of national sports, people's national movement games, physical quality.

Introduction.

In order to educate oneself physically, a person should understand the necessity of physical education and sports and diligently form his health based on a certain system of physical training that he likes. Comprehensive development of the physical abilities of the young generation is carried out in the process of physical education, which is an integral part of education. The goal of physical education is a long-term, organized pedagogical process of educating healthy, cheerful, all-round physically developed builders of the society, who are ready for work and defense of the Motherland. Today, the need to collect national movement games of the people and apply them to life, to use them rationally, in solving the tasks facing physical education is evident today.

Literature Analysis And Methodology

The most important issue is the proper organization and conduct of lessons and exercises based on action games for the development of the physical qualities of a primary school student. According to the research of K. Balsevich, he describes the physical activity of children. The results of physical training according to the indicators of F.N. Nasriddinov, A.Sh. Kasimov show that all indicators increase by a certain amount with age. Some sharp stages are defined in the dynamics of age change, which are characterized by a set of morphological and functional features. In order to further enliven the health-educational work of elementary school students with the help of mobile games, it is necessary to determine the correlation between their physical development and the indicator of readiness. This provides an opportunity to choose effective tools, and then conduct pedagogical tests and experiments.

Results.

It is also necessary to pay attention to such aspects as the spirit, nature, character, and behavior of the participants of the games of elementary school students. The same features should be taken into account when using some of the national games that we recommend in order to make the physical education of elementary school students interesting and useful. Instilling love for values in physical education classes in elementary school students, teaching them to carefully preserve national traditions depends to a large extent on the ability to effectively use the national movement games of the people. The reason is that, on the one hand, the child acquires physical knowledge through national movement games, and on the other hand, it is important to interest him in physical education, thereby, in values. Age-appropriate games for 1-4 grade children can be divided into the following groups according to the development of physical qualities:

- Games that train agility and flexibility in children;
- Games that increase strength in children.
- Games that develop endurance and agility in children.

Certain types of games can be suitable for all joints of children, that is, there are many games aimed at educating physical qualities as a whole, in which different physical qualities can be developed sequentially. In the process of using national mobile games, the following characteristics of primary school students should be taken into account: Increasing interest of the elementary school student in adult activity, their attitude to subjects and mutual treatment and attitude.

Children's folk action games reflect the most outwardly expressive, passionate emotional aspects of the surrounding reality.

In mobile games, elementary school students can put their desires into practice, feeling that they are living in the same conditions and on the same ground as adults.

Both the people and the society are interested in the young generation being physically fit, healthy, ready to defend the Motherland, growing up energetically. they need to master the skill of using yin. This is related to the extremely important tasks of increasing attention to the education of the young generation, raising them in the spirit of feeling their duty to their nation, independent state and society. it will be possible to finish the work, to form the characteristics of stability. Along with all the modern means of physical education, the national movement games of the Uzbek people are very useful, because these games can include all aspects of raising children mentally,

physically, and spiritually. After all, educating young people, who are the future of the nation, to be healthy, mature and perfect people will serve to strengthen the foundation of the future of our independent country. We mentioned above that action games and national sports have changed significantly in the course of historical development, and each economic system has left its own mark on their content and rules. The names and rules of some games have been preserved for now. When using such games, it is necessary not to lose sight of the fact that they have an educational effect on children in addition to their physical effects, and to coordinate their creative use. For example, the game "Uloq" refers to the ancient game of kopkari, usually played on horseback, where riders fight for a real goat.

Conclusion:

It is known that in order to correctly determine the physical education, physical development and readiness of children from a methodical and pedagogical point of view, it is necessary to know well the physiology and psychology of children. The number of tasks is two to three, they are divided into several groups, basic movements and exercises, and national movement games are selected. The selected exercises should be related to the main movements. Secondly, the exercises should be suitable for the age, level of training and gender of the students. In addition, these exercises should be simple, understandable, familiar to the child and they should be able to perform them.

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